

POLYPHEM

Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle

D2.2 Recovery Heat Exchanger

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SUMMARY	<p>This document is the deliverable D2.2 of the project POLYPHEM. It is planned in the framework of the Work Package 02.</p> <p>The document describes the technical specifications for the design of the air/oil recovery heat exchanger. Drawings and a picture of the unit are also shown.</p> <p>The content of this deliverable fully complies with the Grant Agreement number 764048 signed between the beneficiaries and the European Commission. It also complies with the project Consortium Agreement signed by the beneficiaries. This deliverable cannot replace the role neither of the Grant Agreement nor of the Consortium Agreement, which are evidence for the project.</p>
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Background: about the POLYPHEM project

FULL TITLE	SMALL-SCALE SOLAR THERMAL COMBINED-CYCLE
Acronym	POLYPHEM
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Instrument	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
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Beneficiaries	CNRS, CEA, CIEMAT, Arraela S.L., Fraunhofer ISE, Kaefer Isoliertechnik, Orcan Energy, Euronovia, Aalborg CSP

The POLYPHEM project is a research and innovation action funded by the European Union's H2020 program. It is implemented by a European consortium of 4 research centers and 5 industrial partners. The aim is to increase the flexibility and improve the performance of small solar tower power plants. The concept of POLYPHEM consists in implementing a combined cycle formed by a solarized micro gas-turbine and a Rankine organic cycle machine, with an integrated thermal storage device between the two cycles. The need for cooling is minimal.

Developed from a patented technology by CNRS and CEA, the pressurized air solar receiver is integrated in the micro-turbine cycle. The thermal efficiency targeted for the receiver is 80% with a cost of 400 €/kW. The innovative thermal storage uses a thermal oil and a single thermocline tank with a technical concrete filler material.

The main expected impact of this project is to enhance the competitiveness of low-carbon energy production systems through the technology developed. The expected progress is a better fitting of electricity generation to variable local needs, an overall conversion efficiency of solar energy into electricity of 18% for an investment cost of less than 5 €/W and a low environmental impact. By 2030, the cost of electricity production targeted by the POLYPHEM technology is 165 €/MWh for an annual direct normal irradiation of 2600 kWh/m²/year (North Africa and Middle East) and 209 €/MWh under 2050 kWh/m²/year (Southern Europe). In addition to decentralized power generation, other applications are considered for the deployment of this technology used in poly-generation: industrial heat production, solar heating and cooling, desalination of seawater or brackish water.

A prototype plant of 60 kW_{el} with a thermal storage of 1300 kWh is designed, built and installed on the site of the experimental solar tower of Themis in Targassonne (France). The objective of the project is to validate the technical choices under test conditions representative of actual operating conditions.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/abbreviation	Meaning/full text
AALB	Aalborg CSP
ARRA	Arraela S.L.
CA	Consortium Agreement
CEA	Commissariat à l’Energie Atomique
CIEMAT	Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas, Medioambientales y Tecnologicas
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
CO	Confidential
D	Deliverable
DBT	Dibenzyltoluene
EU	European Union
EURO	Euronovia
FISE	Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems, ISE
HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid
M	Month
MS	Milestone
ORC	Orcan Energy GmbH or Organic Rankine Cycle
PU	Public
WP	Work Package

1. DEMONSTRATOR FOR RHX (RECOVERY HEAT EXCHANGER).

1.1 TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS

The Recovery Heat exchanger (RHX) , utilizing the energy in the exhaust gas from the micro turbine to heat up the thermal oil loop, has been designed based on the latest technical specifications of the outlet flow from the Micro Turbine from Kaefer. The thermal oil used as heat transfer fluid (HTF) has been selected in WP3 of the project. This oil is a synthetic oil named Jarytherm® DBT. The technical datasheet of Jarytherm® DBT is given in Annex.

As available space is limited for the heat exchanger in the existing Themis Solar Tower, the design is based on tubes with extended heating surface. Among the various possibilities available, serrated spiral fins welded to the heating surface pipes gives the best performance/space ratio. Further distributing the spiral fins as narrow as possible using laser welding technic, a maximum density of fins per meter tube is obtained (see figure 3).

The results of the thermodynamically calculations have given the following performance and geometry for the exhaust gas/oil heat exchanger:

Table 1: Performance of the RHX at design conditions

Exhaust gas flow (kg/s)	0.82
Gas temperature inlet (°C)	495
Gas temperature outlet (°C)	99
Pressure loss gas side (Pa)	221
HTF flow (kg/s)	0.755
HTF temperature inlet (°C)	95
HTF temperature outlet (°C)	300
Heat transferred from gas to HTF (kW)	341
Pressure loss HTF side (Pa)	228100

Table 2: Geometry of the RHX

Tube type	Spiral fin, HF segmented
Tube material	P235GH
Fin material	10CrMo910
Tube configuration	Staggered
Flow direction	Counter
Tube diameter (mm)	25.4
Tube thickness (mm)	3.2
Fin height (mm)	10
Fin thickness (mm)	0.8
Fin pitch (no/m)	300
Tube length (mm)	800
No of tubes across	14
No of tubes in flow direction	24
No of flow ways	2
Pitch across (mm)	50
Pitch in flow direction (mm)	44
Fin tube surface area (m ²)	191.9

1.2 DRAWINGS AND PICTURES OF HEAT EXCHANGER:

Figure 1. External view

Figure 2: Internal view

Figure 3: Serrated fin tube

2. ANNEX: Jarytherm® DBT Technical Datasheet

JARYTHERM® DBT

Heat transfer fluid

Synthetic heat transfer fluid, made from a blend of dibenzyltoluene isomers.

APPLICATIONS

Heat transfer installations
by fluid circulation

- Operating from 0°C to + 350 °C in the bulk (370 °C in the film) without air contact. JARYTHERM® DBT is mainly used in the chemical and plastics transformation industries (barrel extruders).

SPECIFICATIONS

- ISO 6743/12 class L-QD-350

JARYTHERM® DBT successfully passes the following Thermal Stability tests (1000h, 350°C):

- ASTM D6743
- DIN 51528
- GB/T 23800-2009

ADVANTAGES

Extended drain interval

Working safety

- **Excellent stability to thermal cracking**
Can be used for a long period without the formation of carbon deposits which can foul the circuit. Preserves the heat exchange characteristics of the installation.
- **Resistance to oxidation**
A thermal fluid must show good resistance to oxidation, even with limited exposure to oxygen in the air. JARYTHERM® DBT offers this characteristics.

TYPICAL PROPERTIES	METHODS	UNITS	JARYTHERM® DBT			
			20 °C	100 °C	200 °C	300 °C
Density	ISO 3675	kg/m ³	1043	987	914	834
Kinematic viscosity	ISO 3104	mm ² /s	50	3	0.82	0.44
Specific heat capacity	-	kJ/kg °C	1.60	1.81	2.10	2.51
Thermal conductivity	-	W/m °C	0.128	0.121	0.113	0.105

Above characteristics are mean values given as an information.

TOTAL LUBRIFIANTS
INDUSTRIE
12-10-2016 (supersedes 20-01-2016)
JARYTHERM® DBT
1/2

TOTAL

TYPICAL CHARACTERISTICS	METHODS	UNITS	JARYTHERM® DBT
Flash point OC	ISO 2592	°C	200
Fire point	ISO 2592	°C	230
Pour point	ISO 3016	°C	- 34
Boiling point	-	°C	390
(under 760 mm of mercury)			
Total Decomposition Rate – 1000h, 350°C.	GB23800-2009	%	6.9
Operating range	-		
- in the bulk		°C	0 / + 350
- in the film		°C	370

Above characteristics are mean values given as an information.

A few useful conversion factors:

1 Kcal/kg. °C = 4184 J/Kg. °C

1 Kcal/m.h. °C = 1.162 W/m. °C

1 mm Hg = 133 Pa

JARYTHERM® DBT is registered trademark of ARKEMA.

Jarytherm® DBT

Thermodynamic Data

T (°C)	Specific Heat (kJ/kg.°C)	Thermal Conductivity (W/m.°C)	Density (kg/m ³)	Vapour pressure (bar)	Dynamic Viscosity (mPa.s)	Kinematic Viscosity (mm ² /s)
0	1,520	0,130	1059	0,00	274,1	258,8
20	1,580	0,128	1044	0,00	52,3	50,1
40	1,650	0,126	1029	0,00	17,45	17,0
60	1,710	0,125	1014	0,00	7,98	7,87
80	1,780	0,123	1000	0,00	4,43	4,43
100	1,840	0,121	985	0,00	2,80	2,84
120	1,900	0,120	970	0,00	1,94	2,00
140	1,970	0,118	955	0,00	1,43	1,50
160	2,030	0,116	940	0,00	1,11	1,18
180	2,090	0,115	925	0,00	0,89	0,96
200	2,160	0,113	911	0,01	0,74	0,81
220	2,220	0,112	896	0,01	0,62	0,69
240	2,290	0,110	881	0,03	0,54	0,61
260	2,350	0,108	866	0,05	0,47	0,54
280	2,410	0,107	851	0,10	0,42	0,49
300	2,480	0,105	836	0,17	0,37	0,44
320	2,540	0,103	821	0,29	0,34	0,41
340	2,600	0,102	807	0,46	0,31	0,38
360	2,670	0,100	792	0,71	0,28	0,35
380	2,730	0,098	777	1,06	0,26	0,33

TOTAL LUBRIFIANTS
INDUSTRIE
12-10-2016 (supersedes 20-01-2016)
JARYTHERM® DBT
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This lubricant used as recommended and for the application for which it has been designed does not present any particular risk.

A material safety data sheet conforming to the regulations in use in the E.C. can be obtained from your local commercial adviser or down loaded from www.quick-fds.com